

Study Habits and Academic Performance in Physical Education and Health among Grade 11 Senior High School Students at St. Paul University – Surigao

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Abstract

The study habits of a learner are crucial for their academic success, exerting a substantial influence on their performance in school. These habits refer to the recurring inclinations and behaviors that students have while obtaining information through the process of learning. Thus, the primary purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between study habits and students' academic performance. The study utilized a descriptive-correlation design to describe student's portfolio in terms of their sex, strand, and average frequency of studying in a day, significant difference of study habits and academic performance when grouped into profile, and relationship of study habits and academic achievement. A total of three hundred eighteen (318) Grade 11 senior high school learners participated in this study. Moreover, the main research instrument utilized in the study was the adapted and modified Palsane and Sharma Study Habit Inventory. Its 4 sub-scales are physical condition, learning motivation, taking examinations, and health. The findings showed that the respondents' study habits have no significant difference when grouped into profile such as their sex, strand, and average frequency of studying in a day. Study habits and academic performance did not show a statistically significant relationship. Furthermore, the findings indicated a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 11 senior high school students when categorized based on their profiles. In addition, improving students' study habits with regards to their physical condition, learning motivation, taking examinations, and overall health would enhance their frequency of studying and, particularly, their academic performance.

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1. Introduction

Education is essential for achieving a high standard of living. It functions as an essential compass throughout an individual's life and serves as a crucial trigger for profound transformations in individuals. Education provides individuals with knowledge that they may readily absorb and apply in their everyday lives as they continue to gain it. However, education requires learners to possess a range of abilities, tactics, and procedures in order to achieve academic excellence. According to Ebele & Olofu (2017) the manner in which a student approaches their studies has a substantial impact on their performance in school. The level of preparation and the learning techniques that students intentionally build and use have a significant impact on their academic achievement. Thus, study habits are one of the most significant factors influencing students' academic achievements.

Study habits are the core of a learner's academic success. According to Bhat (2022) an effective study habits contribute to good student performance. Study habits involve dedicating uninterrupted time to engage in learning (Rabia, Mubarak, Tallat, & Nasir, 2017). These habits significantly impact a student's success in school. Furthermore, study habits are the habitual tendencies and practices that students exhibit during the process of acquiring information through learning. Various study habits have emerged, encompassing activities such as time management, setting appropriate goals, selecting an optimal study environment, employing effective note-taking strategies, identifying main ideas, and maintaining organization (Kumar, 2015). These methods have been utilized and proven effective by many students, making the studying process more efficient and engaging. In the absence of cultivating effective study habits, learners are unable to excel or enhance their academic performance (Ebele & Olofu, 2017).

On the other hand, academic performance measures a student's academic success. It includes grades, test scores, class participation, assignment completion, and topic mastery. It reflects how well a student performs in their studies, resulting from their hard work and dedication. It pertains to the level of achievement a student demonstrates in their individual courses. Enhancing students' academic performance is a key objective for every educational institution (Alimohamadi, Dehghani, Paymard, & Khalili, 2018). Academic performance in school is the main measure of a high-quality learning experience in all types of schools, especially in higher education institutions (Magulod, 2019). A theory related to academic performance is the one developed by Walberg, which posits that academic productivity depends on three factors:

personal structure (including ability, development, and motivation), teaching (both the amount of information taught and its clarity), and the environment where the student lives and carries out activities such as the home, classroom, peer group outside the classroom, and mass media (Reynolds & Walberg, 1992).

In the study titled "Study Habit and Its Impact on Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Biology in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja," Ebele and Olofu (2017) discovered a significant relationship among study habits and academic performance, providing evidence for the mentioned study above. This implies that students who cultivate effective study habits are more likely to achieve higher academic achievement and improve their overall academic success. The potential influence of study habits on the academic performance of Peruvian university students was examined. The findings of the study confirmed that study habits do have an impact on academic performance (Chilca, 2017). Furthermore, Tus et al. (2020) stated that the findings suggested that the study habits of the participants were moderately average. The findings indicated that there was no statistically significant relationship between study habits and academic success. On the contrary, Jafari et al. (2019) discovered that the majority of medical science students had a moderate level of study habits. They also determined that there exists a direct and significant correlation between study habits and academic performance.

Consequently, the researchers have discovered a possible insufficiency in the current body of literature because there is a dearth of studies undertaken in the specific context of the Philippines on this subject. Previous research consistently indicates a strong association between study habits and academic success. The objective of this study is to assess the current study habits and academic performance of Grade 11 senior high school students. The aim is to enhance their readiness for the upcoming academic year as they approach graduation. The purpose of this study is to identify and address any obstacles or complexities that students may encounter throughout their academic journey. Additionally, it provides extensive solutions to potential issues for youth, educators, parents, guidance counselors, and prospective researchers.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the relationship between Grade 11 - Senior High School learners' study habits and academic performance. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 strand; and
 - 1.3 average frequency of studying in a day?
2. What is the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School students in terms of:

- 2.1 physical condition
- 2.2 learning motivation
- 2.3 taking examinations
- 2.4 health
3. What is the level of academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High School students?
4. Is there a significant difference on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School students when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference between the academic performance and profile of the Grade 11 Senior High School students?
6. Is there a significant relationship between study habits and academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High School students?

Hypothesis

At the 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the study habits of the Grade 11 senior high school students when participants are grouped according to their profile.

At the 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant difference between the academic performance and profile of the Grade 11 senior high school students.

At the 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between study habits and the academic performance of the Grade 11 senior high school students

2. Methodology

The researchers utilized the descriptive-correlation method to look into the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. It is a method in which it doesn't make straight predictions and does not determine cause and effect (Hale, 2018). This study was conducted to the 318 Grade 11 senior high school students. The sampling technique that the researchers utilized for the study was the stratified random sampling method — this kind of sampling is usually used in quantitative research for the purpose of ensuring that every subgroup is well represented to make sure that there is no over representation. The researchers selected an online survey questionnaire as the primary method for data collection to assess the study habits of the respondents. This questionnaire was used to present, evaluate, and interpret the data gathered from the participants. To measure the respondents' academic performance, the researchers

collected the general averages of Grade 11 students for the second semester of the 2023-2024 school year, based on the school's academic records.

The instrument is an adapted and modified utilized in this study was the Palsane and Sharma Study Habits Inventory (PSSHI) developed by M. N. Palsane and Saddhna Sharma to determine the relationship between the study habits and the academic performance of the students (Looyeh, Fazelpour, Masoule, Chehrzad & Leili, 2017). Scoring of the Study Habits Inventory has been done on a three-point rating scale. This instrument contains 25 statements that belong to the four areas: physical condition, learning motivation, taking examinations, and health. The points were rated as "0 = rarely or never", "1 = sometimes" and "2 = Always or Mostly". A higher score indicates good study habits. The reliability coefficient by the test-retest method and split-half technique is .88 and .56, respectively.

V. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Profile	f (318)	%
Sex		
Male	125	39
Female	193	61
Strand		
ABM	59	19
ADT-TVL	22	7
HUMSS	47	15
STEM	190	60
Average Frequency of Studying in a Day 1-2		
hrs.	135	43
2-3 hrs.	118	37
3-4 hrs.	54	17
4-5 hrs.	11	4

Table 1 presents the profile of the selected 318 Grade 11 Senior High school students as to age, strand, and average frequency of studying in a day. Specifically, as to their sex, majority are female with 193 (61%) while 125 (39%) are male. Then, with regards to their strand, mostly are in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand with 190 (60%), followed by Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand with 47 (15%), then Arts and Design Track - Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track (ADT-TVL) strand with 22 (7%), and Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) with 59 (19%). Furthermore, concerning their

average frequency of studying in a day, most of them spent 1-2 hours with 135 (43%), followed by 2-3 hours with 118 (37%), then 3-4 hours with 54 (17%), and 4-5 hours with 11 (4%).

Table 2. The Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students in terms of Physical Condition

<i>Indicators</i>	M	SD	VI
1. I have all the required books and other relevant materials of study with me.	1.24	0.54	A
2. For the time of the study, I get disturbed by the surroundings at the time of the study.	1.43	0.53	H
3. I develop an automatic interest in the subject as soon as I start studying it	1.41	0.58	H
4. I realize the importance of the subjects for my future career.	1.62	0.52	H
5. Other stray thoughts gradually flow in as soon as I settle down for the study.	1.43	0.54	H
6. I think that I can improve my study habits fairly.	1.58	0.52	H
Average	1.45	0.54	H

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation
	1.34 - 2.00	High (H)
21	0.67 - 1.33	Average (A)
0	0.00 - 0.66	Low (L)

Table 2 displays the study habits of the Grade 11 senior high school students in terms of physical condition, it is verbally interpreted as *High* (M=1.45, SD=0.54). This shows that students are in the high level of Physical Condition in the things that they do over a bit of time; they think with a specific goal in mind.

Among the 6 indicators, the item I realize the importance of the subjects for my future career, got the highest mean (M=1.62, SD=0.52), which can be verbally interpreted as *High*. This indicates that the participants perceive their subjects as important and advantageous for their future professional endeavors. When

On the other hand, the item I have all the required books and other relevant materials of study with me, got the lowest mean ($M=1.24$, $SD=0.54$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Sometimes*. It implies that the respondents lack some book and other related materials when they study. The materials nowadays are mostly electronic and sometimes may affect how they acquire information. According to Li and Wang (2024), textbooks should possess significant influence over students' perceptions and serve as the primary and crucial source of learning.

Table 3. The Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students in terms of Learning Motivation

<i>Indicators</i>	M	SD	VI
1. I take the help of anybody if I do not follow anything.	1.45	0.56	H
2. I study the subject matter at home thoroughly before it is taught in the classroom.	1.11	0.65	A
3. I attend my classes regularly on time.	1.63	0.51	H
4. I frequently remain absent from class	0.71	0.78	A
5. If a matter is to be learned by heart, I read and memorize it part by part.	1.47	0.55	H
6. I try to make up my deficiency in the weak subjects to my best.	1.50	0.55	H
Average	1.31	0.60	A

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation
21	1.34 - 2.00	High (H)
0	0.67 - 1.33	Average (A)
	0.00 - 0.66	Low (L)

Table 3 presents the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students, indicating an *Average* level of learning motivation ($M = 1.31$, $SD = 0.60$). This means that the students' motivation toward learning is average. Learning motivation is a determinant of learning outcomes. Motivation strongly influences student performance in accomplishing learning goals (Emda, 2018).

Among the 6 indicators, the item I try to make up my deficiency in the weak subjects to my best got the highest mean ($M=1.50$, $SD=0.55$), which can be verbally interpreted as *High*. This denotes that the students are putting in their best effort to improve and compensate for their lack of knowledge or skills in the subjects where they are not performing well. They are actively working to overcome their weaknesses in those areas.

On the other hand, the item for which I frequently remain absent from class, got the lowest mean ($M=0.71$, $SD=0.78$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Average*. This indicates

that students often do not attend their classes. This implies a regular pattern of missing classes rather than just an occasional absence. According to Happel's (2022), there is a relationship between student attendance and academic performance. It indicates that, in general, there is a significant and positive correlation between the two, meaning that students who attend classes more regularly tend to perform better academically.

Table 4. The Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students in terms of Taking Examinations

<i>Indicators</i>	M	SD	VI
1. During examination days also, I sleep as usual in the night.	1.24	0.64	A
2. Before writing the answers to the questions in the examination, I read very carefully the entire question paper.	1.63	0.51	H
3. In the examination, I answer the question in their serial order.	1.47	0.55	H
4. Before examination, I read my own notes carefully	1.48	0.58	H
5. I prepare for the examinations from the guides/notes available in the market.	1.43	0.63	H
6. I draw an outline of answers of each question, before writing answers to the questions in the examination.	1.37	0.62	H
7. I feel tense at the beginning of the examination.	1.47	0.59	H
8. I carefully record my examination results.	1.23	0.67	A
9. I single out my weak subjects on the strength of my examination results.	1.43	0.56	H
10. I have a tendency to compare my marks with others after the results are declared.	1.36	0.67	H
Average	1.41	0.60	H

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation
	1.34 - 2.00	High (H)
21	0.67 - 1.33	Average (A)
0	0.00 - 0.66	Low (L)

Table 4 displays the study habits of the Grade 11 senior high school students in terms of taking examination, it is verbally interpreted as *High* (M=1.41, SD=0.60). This means students regard their exams with a high level of importance because the results of these exams have a

significant impact on their overall academic success. They understand that doing well on exams is crucial for achieving good grades and progressing in their studies.

Among the 10 indicators, the item Before writing the answers to the questions in the examination, I read very carefully the entire question paper, got the highest mean ($M=1.63$, $SD=0.51$), which can be verbally interpreted as *High*. This denotes that the students take the time to thoroughly read through all the questions on the exam before beginning to write their answers. This careful reading helps them understand the questions better, plan their responses, and manage their time effectively during the exam. It emphasizes that examinations are an effective way to quantify the knowledge acquired by students and to estimate the level of learning achieved (Tus et al. 2020).

On the other hand, the item During examination days also, I sleep as usual in the night. got the lowest mean ($M=1.24$, $SD=0.64$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Average*. This demonstrate that students adhere to their normal sleep schedule in average level and continue to go to bed at their typical bedtime even during the exam period. This implies that they place a high importance on obtaining sufficient rest and do not make significant changes to their sleep routine as a result of exams. Zeek et al. (2015) found that a longer duration of sleep the night before an examination was linked to higher course grades and semester grade point averages (GPAs).

Table 5. The Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students in terms of Health

<i>Indicators</i>	M	SD	VI
1. I get disappointed, if the examination result is not favorable.	1.43	0.58	H
2. I get guidance about proper study habit from my teachers.	1.05	0.71	A

3. I will take advantage of a guidance program in study habits is arranged.	1.24	0.66	A
Average	1.24	0.65	A

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation
	1.34 - 2.00	High (H)
21	0.67 - 1.33	Average (A)
0	0.00 - 0.66	Low (L)

Table 5 presents the health-related study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students, which we interpret as *Average* ($M = 1.24$, $SD = 0.65$). This indicates that some students experience disappointment and struggle to accept their exam results, resulting in unhealthy lifestyle choices. However, others maintain average study habits, seeking guidance from their teachers and utilizing any available guidance programs. According to Terada (2022), stress from exams might lead students to eat poorly, either overeating or choosing unhealthy foods.

Among the 3 indicators, the item I get disappointed, if the examination result is not favorable, got the highest mean ($M=1.43$, $SD=0.58$), which can be verbally interpreted as *High*. This denotes that the students feel unhappy or dissatisfied when their exam results do not meet their expectations or are not as good as they had hoped. This disappointment is a reaction to receiving lower grades or scores than they desired.

On the other hand, the item I get guidance about proper study habit from my teachers. got the lowest mean ($M=1.05$, $SD=0.71$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Average*. This interprets that the students receive advice and direction from their teacher on how to develop effective study practices. This guidance helps them learn better study techniques, time management skills, and strategies for academic success. As a result of these compromised study habits, their academic performance was only average, indicating that their health and wellness directly affected their ability to achieve better academic outcomes.

Table 3. Significant Difference on Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students when grouped to profile

Profile	Factors	F	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Physical Condition	10.693	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Learning Motivation	0.500	0.480	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Taking Examinations	1.003	0.317	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

	Health	1.912	0.168	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Physical Condition	6.492	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Learning Motivation	2.024	0.110	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Strand	Taking Examinations	4.615	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
	Health	3.343	0.020	Reject Ho	Significant
	Physical Condition	9.135	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Learning Motivation	7.192	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Average Frequency of Studying in a Day	Taking Examinations	7.953	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Health	3.745	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant

P-value < 0.05 = Reject Ho

Table 3 presents significant difference on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High school students in terms of physical condition, learning motivation, taking examinations, and health when they are grouped according to their profile such as sex, strand, and average frequency of studying in a day.

Sex

It reveals that there are no significant differences on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High school students in terms of learning motivation ($p=0.480$), taking examinations ($p=0.317$), and health ($p=0.168$) as to their sex considering that respective computed p-values are higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to not rejecting the hypothesis. It implies that male and female students exhibit similar study habits in terms of motivation, exam preparation, and health maintenance. This underscores a level of parity in study behavior within their sex. This suggests that factors influencing study habits, such as motivation, preparation for examinations, and health awareness, are not significantly influenced by gender among Grade 11 Senior High school students. As such, there is a need for gender-neutral support strategies aimed at enhancing overall academic performance and well-being.

On the other hand, it shows that there is significant difference on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High school students in terms of physical condition ($p=0.001$) as to their sex considering that respective computed p-value is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to rejecting the hypothesis. It suggests that male and female students demonstrate distinct study habits when it comes to managing their physical well-being during

study sessions. Such differences may indicate varying approaches to incorporating physical health practices into their study routines. Therefore, tailored support strategies addressing these gender-specific differences in study habits related to physical condition may be beneficial in promoting overall academic performance and well-being among students.

Strand

It reveals that there is no significant difference on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High school students in terms of learning motivation ($p=0.110$) as to their strand considering that respective computed p -value is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to not rejecting the hypothesis. This denotes that students across different academic strands exhibit similar levels of motivation when it comes to learning. This finding suggests a degree of consistency in motivational factors among students, regardless of their chosen academic focus. As such, educational interventions aimed at enhancing learning motivation may be applicable universally across various academic strands, fostering a conducive learning environment and promoting academic success for all students.

On the other hand, it shows that there are significant differences on the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High school students in terms of physical condition ($p=0.000$), taking examinations ($p=0.004$), and health ($p=0.020$) as to their strand considering that respective computed p -values are lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to rejecting the hypothesis. This suggests that students within different academic strands exhibit distinct study habits concerning physical well-being, exam preparation, and health awareness. These differences may reflect varying priorities or challenges faced by students in different academic tracks. Therefore, tailored support strategies addressing these differences in study habits related to physical condition, examination preparation, and health may be essential in optimizing academic performance and promoting overall well-being among students across diverse academic strands.

Average Frequency of Studying in a Day

The study reveals significant differences in the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students in terms of physical condition ($p = 0.000$), learning motivation ($p = 0.000$), taking examinations ($p = 0.000$), and health ($p = 0.011$) compared to their average frequency of

studying in a day. The computed p-values are lower than the expected level of significance of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the hypothesis. The study found that physical conditions are significantly associated with differences in how often student’s study. The Grade 11 students who are in better physical condition might study more frequently in Physical Education and Health than students experiencing physical fatigue, who might study less frequently.

Additionally, learning motivation is significantly associated with differences in study frequency. Students with higher motivation to learn may study more often, while those with lower motivation may study less often. The study found that the practice of preparing for or taking exams is significantly associated with the average frequency of studying. Every semester, Grade 11 students have two exams; those who regularly prepare for exams may study more often compared to those who have fewer exams or prepare less frequently. Finally, students' health is significantly associated with differences in how frequently they study. Students in Grade 11 who are in better health might study more frequently, while those with health issues might study less often. Therefore, implementing tailored support strategies to address these variations in study habits related to physical condition, learning motivation, taking examinations, and health may be crucial in fostering academic success and promoting overall well-being among students.

Table 4. Academic Performance of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students

Academic Performance	f (318)	%
Approaching Proficiency (AP: 80% - 84%)	3	1
Proficient (P: 85% - 89%)	61	19
Advanced (A: 90% and Above)	254	80

Table 4 presents the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High school students. It reveals a notable distribution across three proficiency categories from a total of 318 students. A significant majority, 80% (n=254), achieved an Advanced level, scoring 90% and above, which underscores a high level of academic excellence within this group. Following this, 19% (n=61) of the students reached the Proficient category, with scores ranging from 85% to 89%, indicating strong academic performance that falls just short of the Advanced threshold. A small fraction, comprising 1% (n=3), were classified as Approaching Proficiency, with scores between 80% and 84%. This group is on the verge of reaching proficiency but has not yet attained the higher performance levels of their peers. Overall, the data highlights a predominance of high academic achievement among Grade 11 Senior High School students.

Table 5. Significant Difference the Academic Performance of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students when grouped according to profile

Profile	Factors	r (x, y)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation	
<i>Sex</i>		4.210	0.041	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
<i>Strand</i>		813.687			Reject Ho	Significant
<i>Average Frequency of Studying in a Day</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>		0.021			
		3.287			Reject Ho	Significant

P-value < 0.05 = Reject Ho

Table 4 presents significant difference on the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High school students when they are grouped according to their profile such as sex, strand, and average frequency of studying in a day.

Sex

It shows that there is significant difference on the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High school students as to their sex considering that respective computed p-value ($p=0.041$) is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to rejecting the hypothesis. This suggests that sex is a determining factor in the academic outcomes of these students. The difference in academic performance may be attributed to a variety of factors, including differing learning styles, classroom dynamics, and societal expectations. Understanding these differences can help educators tailor their teaching approaches to better support both male and female students and bridge any performance gaps. The study revealed significant differences in academic performance among male and female students. More precisely, it denotes that female student outperformed male students in how they performed in school (Parajuli & Thapa, 2017). Female students may exhibit higher academic achievement than male students, as seen by higher grades, test scores, and other performance indicators.

Strand

It shows that there is significant difference on the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High school students as to their strand considering that respective computed p-value ($p=0.000$) is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to rejecting the hypothesis. This implies that the chosen academic track significantly impacts student performance. Certain academic tracks might offer curriculum and resources that better align with the students' skills and interests, thereby enhancing their performance. Conversely, other tracks might present challenges that do not align as well with the students' strengths, impacting their

academic outcomes. This insight underscores the importance of providing adequate guidance and counseling for students in selecting their academic tracks to ensure a better match between their abilities and the demands of their chosen paths. The results of the study of Herrera (2019), revealed a significant relationship between the academic tracks or strands selected by Grade 11 students (such as STEM, HUMSS, ABM, ADT/TVL) and their performance in school. Therefore, the selection of a particular academic focus significantly influences students' academic performance. The specified critical value (21.03 at a significance level of 0.05) signifies that the link in the study is statistically significant.

Average Frequency of Studying in a Day

It shows that there is significant difference on the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High school students as to their average frequency of studying in a day considering that respective computed p-value ($p=0.021$) is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to rejecting the hypothesis. This indicates that the frequency of study sessions per day is a significant factor affecting academic performance. Regular study habits likely contribute to better comprehension and retention of material, thereby enhancing academic performance. This emphasizes the need for students to adopt effective study routines and for educators to encourage consistent study practices. Additionally, this finding may prompt the development of structured study schedules and support systems to help students manage their study time effectively. To support this result, a considerable percentage of students exhibit inadequate study habits. More precisely, 54.17% of students fail to finish homework outside of school or engage in note review during school hours. In addition, a significant proportion of students, namely 37.50%, engage in the habit of commencing their exam preparation only the day prior to the exam. This suggests a tendency towards last-minute cramming rather than maintaining a constant and regular study habit. The students are not effectively managing their time for studying. This is likely to have a negative impact on their academic performance as they are not participating in regular and consistent study habits (Salcedo-Relucio, 2019).

Table 6. Significant Relationship on Study Habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students and their Academic Performance

IV	Factors	r (x, y)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
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Academic Performance	Physical Condition	-0.001	0.993	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Learning Motivation	-0.017	0.759	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Taking Examinations	-0.034	0.547	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Health	0.006	0.920	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

P-value < 0.05 = Reject Ho

Table 4 presents significant difference in the study habits of the Grade 11 Senior High School students and their academic performance.

Physical Condition

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students when it comes to their physical condition and academic performance. This is supported by the computed p-value of 0.993, which is higher than the expected level of significance of 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis is not rejected. This suggests that variations in students' physical well-being, such as health status or physical fitness, do not significantly influence how much they study or their academic performance in physical education and health. In practical terms, it means that whether a student is in good or poor physical condition, it does not seem to impact their study habits or academic outcomes.

Learning Motivation

The results indicate that there is no significant difference between the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students in terms of learning motivation and their academic performance. This conclusion is supported by the fact that the computed p-value ($p = 0.759$) is higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis cannot be rejected. This implies that students with varying degrees of motivation to learn in physical education and health, whether highly motivated or less so, tend to have similar study habits and academic performance. Despite differences in motivation levels, students appear to dedicate similar amounts of time and effort to studying, with comparable outcomes in terms of academic achievement.

Taking Examinations

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students when it comes to taking examinations and their academic performance. This is supported by the fact that the computed p-value ($p = 0.547$) is higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis cannot be rejected. This indicates that students who approach their physical education and health examination with

varying attitudes, such as feeling confident or anxious, demonstrate similar study habits and academic performance. Regardless of their feelings about the final examination in physical education and health, students appear to engage in similar study behaviors and achieve comparable academic results.

Health

The data indicates that there is no significant difference in the study habits of Grade 11 senior high school students when it comes to their health and academic performance. This is supported by the fact that the computed p-value ($p = 0.920$) is higher than the expected level of significance, which is 0.05. Therefore, the hypothesis cannot be rejected. This implies that students with different health conditions or levels of physical wellness exhibit similar study habits and academic performance. Whether students are in good health or experiencing health challenges, they appear to dedicate comparable amounts of time and effort to studying the Physical Education and Health subject, with similar outcomes in terms of academic achievement.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the study results, we can conclude that there is no significant relationship between Grade 11 senior high school students' study habits and their academic performance in physical education and health. Therefore, we do not reject the hypothesis. Nevertheless, there exists a significant difference between the academic performance in physical education and health and the profile of the students, including their sex, strand, and average frequency of daily studying. Based on this finding, the researchers suggest investigating the perceptions of academic achievement among male and female students. They also propose enhancing this study by including qualitative research methodologies such as interviews, focus groups, and surveys. Additionally, establish mechanisms to systematically collect and assess student feedback regarding their experiences in each area. Use this information to improve and perfect instructional methods, curriculum creation, and support services. Finally, it is crucial to support initiatives that promote students' comprehensive health and well-being, as these can directly impact their ability to participate in consistent studying. These may include stress management courses, physical fitness programs, and mental health support services.

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